

IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL SIGNATURE WITH RSA AND HONEYPOT TO ENHANCE THE DATA SECURITY OF CLOUD IN CLOUD COMPUTING

Salimova Husniya Rustamovna¹,
Ganiyev Asadullo Mahmud o'g'li²

¹ Master's degree, Faculty of Cyber-Security, Tashkent University Of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan

² Bachelor degree, Faculty of Software engineering, Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

The cloud is a next generation platform that provides dynamic resource pools, virtualization, and high availability. Today, we have the ability to utilize scalable, distributed computing environments within the confines of the Internet, a practice known as cloud computing. Cloud computing is the Concept Implemented to decipher the Daily Computing Problems, likes of Hardware Software and Resource Availability unhurried by Computer users. The cloud Computing provides an undemanding and Non ineffectual Solution for Daily Computing.

Introduction: Currently cloud computing has been used by many organization, because of its benefits like total cost decrease and ease of access of data. Multi cloud storage is recently being popular through its several advantages. Though there are many benefits by using cloud computing the security breaches make some of the users to step out of using it, as they share confidential data with cloud storage providers but, they may be untrusted. We proposed to develop modified RSA algorithm, which is extensively used in the popular implementations of Public Key Infrastructures. In asymmetric key cryptography, also called Public Key cryptography, two different keys (which

form a key pair) are used. One key is used for encryption & only the other corresponding key must be used for decryption. By using RSA algorithm and implementation with the digital signature (DSS). we provide data integrity over a multi cloud. Assurance of data integrity that is data remain as it is on server for long time. In our proposed research we will combine RSA with HMAC function. We provide data integrity in the secure network transaction over a multi cloud. It depends on multi cloud so, to share confidential data between clouds and to prevent them from hackers. We will also generate there digital signature by using different mechanisms. This paper will focus on some of the integrity proving

techniques in detail along with their limitations.

In IT industry cloud provides three services SaaS, PaaS, IaaS. Cloud computing is a network where the user can use services providing by CSP on pay per use bases. This kind of technology helps users for handling resources effectively on-site. So the challenging factor on multicloud is strong data security and transaction mechanism over a multi cloud. Mostly the data are stored in clouds are highly sensitive. For example, financial records and social networks. Gain the strong security over the transaction on multicloud is very much important. So, in the system provides data integrity and verified valid services to authorized users in multicloud. The process authentication is initiated for all valid transactions that is been performed.

Materials: CS (cloud server) will compute a hash value from the original data to send it to the TPA, and then takes this hash value along with the data signed in the cloud for verify using the public key. At the end, the CS will inform the user if the data in the cloud modified or not.

Methods: User first chose a random parameter to develop the public and the private keys then user will sign the data using the private key to be uploaded to the cloud, then user sends the signed data to the cloud server and deletes its local copy

Results: We studied all level of interaction honeypots and configured them. As first level of interaction honeypot, we deployed Honeyd. We explained the logic behind it and installed it correctly. Our findings about Honeyd are; Honeyd is the most popular low interaction honeypot but its problem is its age. The project is opensource but part of it is outdated and nobody seems to upgrade it. On the other hand hacker tools are

evolving, so identifying this honeypot is not hard. Honeyd is using an old version on Nmap fingerprint to create fake virtual operating systems so by using a newer version of Nmap, the fake operating systems will not be recognized and Nmap will detect that there is a problem. Another limitation of Honeyd is the scripts bound to the different ports. With a basic scan it is possible to find which ports are open but as soon as the attacker tries to actually connect on a port, he will realize the service is fake. For example the script used for a Web server, by connecting it using telnet, the server should send back replies but nothing is happening. Another problem is one cannot understand if there is an incoming attack to the system or not. Because there is no such alarm system that can make you understand that there is an attack. Information gathering is not very smart either. As a result the hacker can understand quickly that there is something wrong with the target and will abort his attack. Even unprofessional intruders can compromise the honeypot without spending too much time on it. Because it is very popular and easy to use well known techniques such as Nmap. There is no additional approach needed for it. Our second step was to configure medium level interaction honeypot Nepenthes. We explained how it works and how we studied on it in implementation part. However, we found some problems with Nepenthes too. First of all, Nepenthes is for capturing malware over internet. It is mostly used for this aim. Thus, it must be implemented very rapidly since threats for users over internet are increasing dramatically day by day. Nepenthes could not keep up with new threats. As new threats are arriving and Nepenthes is not up to date, it will not be

able to capture malware. Another problem comes from the shellcode. Shellcode manager should consider about shellcode and understand it. As new threats cannot be captured, new exploits cannot be captured either. Furthermore, as we are investigating the problems and security flaws in our experiment, there is an important security flaw in Nepenthes structure. Nepenthes do not have transport layer security. Transport layer security is a protocol that gives security for communications throughout the internet. We think it is a real problem for honeypot deployment. Some malware exist on port 445 that are being involved with each other which are "LSASS, PNP, DCOM, ASN1, ms06-070, ms08-067". When this kind of interference happens, we are not sure about the replies either. It creates a big mess between modules. (Schloesser M., (2009)). Figure 8.1 is showing the attacks observed according to Maheswari V. & Sankaranarayanan Dr.P.E., (2007).

securely storage on cloud and how it will be implemented. They implement the digital signature on it with the use of RSA algorithm. In which they are found how digital signature will be implemented by only using RSA algorithm. At very first they use the RSA algorithm for data authentication which are stored at cloud and they also implement the digital signature for verify the users data which are stored on cloud. Thus, mainly there area of research is about provide data storage security on cloud. 2) Secure Cloud Storage Model with Hidden Policy Attribute based Access Control Abstract Implementing Digital Signature with RSA Encryption Algorithm to Enhance the Data Security of Cloud in Cloud Computing (IJSRD/Vol. 4/Issue 01/2016/148) All rights reserved by www.ijsrd.com 546 [7]We propose a

secure cloud storage model that prominently addresses security and storage issues in cloud. These security is achieved by anonymous authentication of the users; where the attributes associated with individual users are hidden from cloud. [8]This helps the cloud users to remain anonymous as well authenticated, for this digital signature based authentication scheme is developed.[9] Also, a decentralized architecture is implemented for distributed key management.[10] Further, Query driven approach is developed for hiding the access policies defined by individual user for his data i.e. the access is granted to the requester only if his credentials matches with the access policy.[11] Homomorphism encryption scheme is used for encrypting the data that is stored in cloud.[12] These data are sometimes vulnerable to loss or damages. In order to address this issue, an automatic retrieval mechanism is developed where the lost data is retrieved automatically.

Conclusion: In this paper they will focus on data storage and security issues on cloud. They will see some problems on bases of cloud which is types of architecture ,access control methods and the authentication techniques. They will reduce this problems over a cloud by implementing multiple KDS structure. in which they will develop a one type of structure that will reduce some problem for security and user authentication on cloud. In that structure the users don't know about their authenticated and their attributes are hidden from cloud by implementing digital signature algorithm. by using access method they will hide the users individuals files from cloud by implementing query based method. Further they enhance the storage based security issues, such as they

will used homophonic encryption techniques for outsourced data. in cloud they will face also some issues related to data lost or leakage. This issue will reduced by implementing string matching algorithm it automatically match the string of data and retrieved easily

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In early years there are various technologies are updated by RSA algorithm. And very high level security achieved by using RSA and digital signature algorithm. But there are some limitation that can not provide highly sufficient and secure transaction of huge amount of data over a cloud. Our system provides higher efficiency and construct high security on all types of cloud.in our system we proposed to develop the RSA higher efficeance algorithm and TPA for authentication our data over perform transaction on cloud and apply the digital signature on that TPA through verify the sender and also apply on that HMAC function for hashing the key value on cloud. thus, experimental results showed that the proposed RSA and digital signing algorithm is more efficient than other signature algorithm used on cloud.

References:

1. Uma Somani,Kanika Lakhani and Manish Mundra , 'Implementing Digital Signature with RSA Encryption Algorithm to Enhance the Data Security of Cloud in Cloud Computing" ,978-1-4244-7674-9/10/\$26.00 ©2010 IEEE
2. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_computing
3. <http://www.cloudcomputing china.cn/Article/1 uilan/200909/306.html>
4. http://searchcloudcomputing.techtarget.com/s Definition/0, sid201_gci1287881,00.html
5. <http://www.boingboing.net/2009/09/02/cloudcomputing -skep.html>
6. (U.S.) Nicholas. Carr, fresh Yan Yu, "IT is no longer important: the Internet great change of the high round - cloud computing," The Big Switch: Rewining the world from Edison to Google, CITIC ublishing House, October 2008 1-1
7. M. Sowmiya, PG Student and M. Adimoolam, Assistant Professor , "Secure Cloud Storage Model with Hidden Policy Attribute based Access Control" ,978-1- 4799- 4989-2/14/\$31.00 © 2014 IEEE

8. S. Ruj, M. Stojmenovic and A. Nayak, "Decentralized Access Control with Anonymous Authentication of Data Stored in Cloud", IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing, pp. 556–563, 2013
9. S. Jahid, P. Mittal and N. Borisov, "EASiER: Encryption-based access control in social networks with efficient Re-vocation," in ACM ASIACCS.
10. Kan Yang, Xiaohua Jia and Kui Ren, 'DAC-MACS: Effective Data Access Control for Multi-Authority Cloud Storage Systems', IACR Cryptology e-Print Archive, pp 419, 2012.
11. D. R. Kuhn, E. J. Coyne, and T. R. Weil, "Adding attributes to role-based access control," IEEE Computer, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 79–81, 2010.
12. C. Wang, Q. Wang, K. Ren, N. Cao and W. Lou, "Toward Secure and Dependable Storage Services in Cloud Computing", IEEE T. Services Computing, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 220–232, 2012.
13. Hur and Kun Noh, "Attribute-Based Access Control with Efficient Revocation in Data outsourcing Systems", IEEE Trans. Parallel Distrib. Syst., vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 1214–1221, 2011.
14. Dr. Vinayak Ashok Bharadi and Mr. Godson Michael D'silva, "Online Signature Recognition using Software as a Service (SaaS) Model on Public Cloud" ,978-1- 4799-6892-3/15 \$31.00 © 2015 IEEE DOI 10.1109/ICCUBE.2015.208
15. H B Kekre, V A Bharadi , "Dynamic signature preprocessing by modified digital difference analyzer algorithm" , Springer India, Thinkquest, pp 67-73, 2011.